

Why and how to evaluate Trustworthiness in AI

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Abstract. While traditional performance indicators help compare AI systems based on technical efficiency, they fail to capture critical user-related aspects such as perceived AI trustworthiness, which impedes acceptance and long-term adoption. Perceived AI trustworthiness offers avenues for user-centered evaluations of AI solutions across use cases or iterative design phases, but existing evaluation tools lack a clear and operationalizable definition of perceived trustworthiness. Thus, we present a simple framework with distinct measurable constructs (e.g., comprehensibility, technical functioning) grounded in established models. Additionally, we present an overview of existing trustworthiness assessment tools, analyzing their strengths and limitations. This work contributes to the broader goal of fostering AI systems that can be trusted, accepted, and effectively integrated into practice.

Keywords: Trustworthy AI, User experience, Adoption, Acceptance

1 Introduction

The rapid expansion of Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools offers unprecedented opportunities for supporting human decisions in industrial settings. Yet, it also introduces a significant complexity in evaluating, selecting, and deploying the most suitable AI solution: how can stakeholders systematically evaluate which system to trust and adopt? While traditional technical performance indicators provide valuable insights into efficiency and accuracy, they fail to capture essential human-centered factors regarding users' perceptions towards AI systems. Yet, metrics that quantify subjective experiences and human judgments are critical [13, 5] to anticipate the acceptance processes for novice users. This gap is particularly critical in contexts where AI is involved in decision-making, risk assessment, or human-AI teaming. In such contexts, the perceived trustworthiness directly influences system acceptance and adoption.

Several frameworks attempt to represent trustworthiness, such as ALTAI (Assessment List for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence) [2]. However, they often overlook end-users and are not fully suited for collaborative contexts with an AI-assisted sequential-decision making. In this sense, as part of PEER European Research project, we introduce a structured framework intended to guide the selection and development of usable instruments dedicated to measuring perceived AI trustworthiness, fostering assessments beyond purely technical criteria.

2 The acceptance process of AI systems

2.1 Acceptance models and AI trustworthiness

Technology adoption is considered a multi-phase process starting with acceptability (a priori intention), and acceptance (several uses), and then adoption (persistent use). During these several stages, an end-user (i.e. the person that is intended to ultimately use the AI system) will make estimations and evaluations of the advantages, disadvantages, and limits of the AI technology used. This is widely studied within the well-established technology acceptance models such as UTAUT2 [28] that propose factors such as perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness, habits or hedonic motivation to explain the intention to use and current use of the technology. However, this might not be sufficient or applicable to the context of intention to use AI devices [9] as acceptance models can overlook some key aspects of planned human behavior [1]. Beyond ease of use or usefulness, assessing various aspects of perceived trustworthiness is considered especially informative in the context of AI applications. Indeed, trust has a demonstrated importance in the AI domain [7, 24] as autonomous functioning introduces risks, vulnerability and uncertainties which are a prerequisite to trust [18, 14]. A foundational principle of trust models [19] is the distinction between trust and trustworthiness. The first one refers to a person's willingness to rely on another entity despite uncertainty (an attitude of the trustor), while the second refers to the qualities or attributes that influence the decision to trust (a property of the trustee). Hence, trust remains challenging attitude to reliably measure, as it is dynamic and fluctuant based the task and context [18] and depending on current and past AI behavior [21].

We argue that the verification and validation of AI technologies can and should include an evaluation of perceived AI trustworthiness, i.e., the human interpretation of the inherent qualities or stable attributes of the system based on its known characteristics and on the information provided around and during interaction [22, 14]. Thus, our focus is to identify a group of constructs that can be reliably measured when assessing users' overall perception of the systems' qualities rather than a reliance attitude [8] or an emotional response to a specific task or situation.

2.2 Factors of AI trustworthiness

Extensive work has been conducted in determining the factors that contribute to AI acceptance [10, 6, 13, 23], often including trustworthiness-related aspects. As part of a broader effort, a very large landscape of policy documents, guidelines and principles has emerged to provide practical definitions of ethical AI [15] or trustworthy AI [26]. One of the most commonly established is the seven requirements of the ALTAI checklist [2], a regulatory framework that integrates ethical guidelines in AI development and deployment as part as the European approach to fostering global trustworthiness in AI. These practical frameworks focus on functional aspects of trustworthy AI design with few emphasis on the subjective

judgment and emotion [3]. They are design guidelines and are not intended as human-centered metrics of users’ perceptions, i.e. they focus on whether an AI system can be made trustworthy by design, not on whether it will actually be perceived as trustworthy by users. Typically, the ALTAI checklist [2] includes elements that cannot be subjectively assessed by the end-user or would likely not show user-specific variation in the answers’ distribution. For example, in the “Human agency and oversight” part of the ALTAI checklist, expert auditors determine whether the AI uses unfair manipulation to interfere with their decision making process, or whether or not humans have been given specific training on how to exercise oversight. Similarly, in the “Technical Robustness and Safety” part of this checklist, core elements refer to cybersecurity certifications and technical compliance to specific norms of which novice end-users would not be informed in most cases. While very relevant in the context of expert-oriented checklists, these items cannot be used as a direct measurement with end-users.

To bridge this gap and address user-centered perceived trustworthiness and acceptance factors (such as the hedonic motivation from the UTAUT2 model [28]), we can turn to User eXperience (UX) models. Indeed, the UX models offer a complementary approach to understanding and formalizing user’s perceptions over the characteristics of the AI system and the context within which the interaction occurs. In such models, users’ perceptions are divided into two categories [27]: the perception of instrumental qualities (pragmatic) and the perception of non-instrumental qualities (hedonic). On the one hand, the instrumental qualities (pragmatic) include effectiveness (how accurate is the AI), efficiency (how effectiveness relates to the effort and time invested), learnability (how easy is it for users to operate the system the first times they encounter the AI) or memorability (how easy it is for users to re-establish proficiency after a period of non-use). On the other hand, the non-instrumental qualities (hedonic) focus on the psychological well-being of users, induced e.g. by aesthetic, identification, or motivating stimulations. The experience of both instrumental and non-instrumental qualities leads to emotional reactions, which shape the overall users’ appraisal of the AI system according to UX models.

Overall, the AI acceptance process is steered by users’ perception of multiple factors, including human characteristics (e.g. demographics), fixed system properties (e.g. interaction modality, autonomy level, AI model or algorithm, embodiment and anthropomorphic characteristics), and task characteristics (e.g., users’ expertise, task context, environment, and Human-AI relationship factors). Users perceive the system properties, making them signals to build a judgment of trustworthiness which, in turn, influence users’ attitude towards using the AI system. A simple summary of the AI adoption process focused on perceived trustworthiness is shown in Figure 1.

3 An user-centered framework for AI trustworthiness

We propose a first version of an user-centered framework to operationalize perceived trustworthiness through ten core constructs (Figure 2) retained for their

Fig. 1. A summary of the AI adoption process

relevance and collective contribution to perceived trustworthiness. The framework differs from design-centered models by focusing on capturing human judgments over system attributes. While this list does not yet reflect a weighted or empirically validated model, it offers a structured vocabulary and useful foundations to support the future assessments and discussions over perceived AI trustworthiness.

To build this framework, we explored the following question: “What shapes users’ perception of trustworthiness in an AI assistant?”. We started from the basis of the ALTAI framework which relies on 7 technology-centered constructs, then iteratively enriched this framework with human-centered research related to the evaluation of perceived trustworthiness in other application areas: robotics, avionics, human collaboration. To ground the development of our framework in real-world industry practice, we also conducted three socio-technical requirements workshops and semi-structured interviews with end-users. These complementary domains lead us to re-organize sub-constructs from ALTAI. For example, the “Technical Robustness and Safety” construct (ALTAI) has been split into “Technical Functioning” and “Safety Security and Well-being”. Accordingly, we added some new constructs: anthropomorphism, collaboration and components of user experience.

User-centred trustworthiness framework				
User agency	Technical functioning	Safety, security and well-being	Privacy and data governance	Comprehensibility
Ethics	Auditability	Collaboration	Components of user experience	Anthropomorphism

Fig. 2. Ten key constructs to capture the perceived trustworthiness of an AI system

First, *user agency* (C1) refers to the perceived user autonomy offered by the AI system (independent acts without over-relying on the system) and feeling of control (e.g. does the AI assistant follow my directions?) and how the implemented governance mechanism is satisfying for the user.

Next, *technical functioning* (C2) refers to the overall subjective performance of the system (i.e. does the AI assistant perform its job well?) which encompasses perceived accuracy, correctness, reliability when facing new situations and new data, efficiency as in working quickly enough, and consistency over similar situ-

ations. *Safety, security and well-being* (C3) encompasses the perception of how errors can be and are managed (i.e. detected, anticipated, avoided, reduced and corrected), as well as how the AI is perceived as vulnerable to attacks, capable to warn people of potential risks, how user perceive that the AI is concerned about their welfare and would not knowingly do things to hurt them or others.

Next, *privacy and data governance* (C4) is the user-centered subjective pendant of its ALTAI equivalent [2], including the user’s view on data protection, data collection, access to data structure, or the appropriateness of the training data used. *Comprehensibility* (C5) is the overall perceived clarity (i.e. whether the user can form a mental model and predict future system behavior) and learnability of the AI, as a result of the various design processes of explainability, interpretability and traceability. *Ethics* (C6) refers to how the user perceives that the AI considers diversity, non-discrimination, cultures, languages, accessibility, social impact on jobs and skills, or environmental friendliness. *Auditability* (C7) refers to the extent to which users believes that the inner processes, decisions, data, algorithms and outcomes of the AI system can be traced and (independently) verified for an inspection or external audit.

Then, *Collaboration* (C8) refers to the perceived dynamics of teaming between the user and the AI system. It encompasses how the AI gives feedback and (openly) communicates, how the user feels supported by the AI, how the AI considers user’s feedback, the extent to which it allows for personalization or customization. *Anthropomorphism* (C9) refers to the attribution of humanlike characteristics or mental states to the AI (e.g. intentions, emotions, free will, mind or consciousness).

Finally, *others components of user experience* (C10) broadens the framework to include all UX aspects [27], i.e. both the instrumental qualities (e.g., perceived usefulness, perspicuity) and non-instrumental components (e.g., novelty or stimulation).

4 Existing measures of perceived AI trustworthiness

Measuring perceived trustworthiness remains a complex challenge, with a variety of approaches developed to capture this multifaceted construct. Extensive work has been conducted regarding trust assessment for technologies [16, 29], although most of them focus on momentary or context-dependent trust attitudes (including behavioral observations or physiological predictors) rather than users’ perception of system attributes that underpin trust. Among the wide range of user-centered methods, the most common and practically valuable approach for assessing perceived trustworthiness remains the use of questionnaires which offer standardized, repeatable, scalable, and low-cost way to capture users’ subjective perceptions facing AI applications. These existing questionnaires range from single-item surveys to large in-depth scales. While most of these questionnaires come from the field of robotics [22] and automation [17, 30], there are some AI-specific questionnaires already targeting AI device use acceptance [9] or focused

on sub-aspects of trustworthiness such as anthropomorphism [20], transparency [10] or explainability [13].

Taken individually, existing questionnaire fall short when it comes to evaluating the full spectrum of perceived AI trustworthiness. Many are limited in scope, targeting only a subset of relevant constructs identified in the precedent section. Additionally, combining existing scales is not an option as it would introduce important redundancies and inflate response time. In this sense, we are developing a dedicated, multifactorial questionnaire that builds on established instruments and operationalizes the ten core constructs of perceived trustworthiness defined in our framework.

5 Discussion

There are tensions inherent to measuring attribute perception. Notably, a trade-off can be observed between predictors of trustworthiness, e.g. accuracy vs. interpretability, especially in complex or opaque AI models [4]. Moreover, although the different aspects of perceived trustworthiness rely on relatively stable attributes, the perception of these attributes has multiple facets (ethical principles are not universal) and is likely to fluctuate and to vary at different steps of AI information processing [26]. Whenever possible, trustworthiness metrics should go along with qualitative measures to mitigate the risk of under-reporting a construct that would be useful or important for users.

Additionally, in real-life scenario, essential factors account for (and control) potential biases [12, 23, 22]. Notably, contextual factors should be accounted to in accordance to each use-case e.g. task familiarity or perceived risk. Typically, an AI application can be considered trustworthy for a specific task and not for another [25]. Human-related factors such as demographics also need to be addressed, some the most significant factors for technology adoption being culture and age [12]. On a broader level, AI-specific human attitudes should be assessed to explain the measurement outcomes. This includes the propensity to trust AI technologies (i.e. general tendency to trust), the willingness and motivation to use AI technologies (i.e. user’s general attitude towards AI use grounded in psychological, emotional, ethical or practical reasons) or anxiety towards AI. Further factors also include general effort expectancies, technological self-efficacy, AI literacy, or the users’ trust in the AI stakeholders themselves [11].

6 Conclusion

We introduce a human-centered evaluation framework synthesized from established models of acceptance and interdisciplinary insights and designed to provide a common vocabulary to support decisions about which AI systems are not only functional and well-designed but also accepted and actually perceived as trustworthy by their end-users.

In a field where the successful adoption of AI involves more than technical AI design, we promote human-centered constructs as key user indicators collected

from the users' subjective point of view to complement technical benchmarks. Looking ahead, the framework will be refined through the iterative user testing of a comprehensive questionnaire across diverse industrial AI settings in a reproducible manner, providing further insights into its practical application to real-world industrial scenarios.

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